

Personal Factors Impacting Students' Mathematical Learning Across the Transition from Primary to Post-Primary: Insights from Literature

John Behan

School of STEM Education, Innovation and Global Studies, Dublin City University

Among the many factors influencing a student's experience of the transition from primary to post-primary are those related to the individual students themselves. This paper provides insights from literature into such personal characteristics, examining how they impact on the transition and in particular on students' mathematical learning. While a wide range of such factors exist, this paper focuses on gender, special education needs and adolescence. As evidenced in this paper, the involvement of so many factors make the transition to post-primary school a very different experience for individual students in terms of their mathematical learning, with some encountering more barriers and challenges than others. Accordingly, a single one-size-fits-all approach or support would appear difficult to conceive and unreasonable to expect.

Introduction

The transition from primary to post-primary has been identified as a significant time for student learning, particularly in the area of mathematics. The transition from primary to post-primary is viewed not merely as a physical event, but as a process spanning across the final year of primary school and the first year of post-primary. Reflecting the intricacy of this transition, Hargreaves, Earl and Ryan (1996) describes the "triple change" that learners face during this time; changes that are social, physical and intellectual in nature. Many studies highlight the significance of the primary to post-primary transition in the lives of learners; their experiences of the process are seen to influence their subsequent perspectives and outcomes (Smyth, 2017), as well as having an impact on their mental health and wellbeing (White, 2020). Set in the time of great physical and emotional change, the transition from primary to post-primary school presents adolescent students with a myriad of new experiences, emotions and potential tipping points (Tilleczek, 2007). While the exploration of all factors, whether personal, social or those related to the school environment, is beyond the scope of this paper, it is important to highlight the vast extent of change at play in the lives of learners at this time.

A Time of Challenge and Opportunity for Students

The transition to post-primary school is commonly presented in literature in terms of the challenges and difficulties experienced, with the proportion of students who have been found to experience such difficulties varying among studies. In the large-scale Australian study, almost one third of students (31%) claimed to have experienced a difficult transition (Waters et al., 2012), while in Scotland, a majority of students at the end of first year of post-primary recalled having difficulties during the transition (West et al., 2010). In Ireland, it was found that a small cohort of students experienced sustained difficulties during the transition,

with certain cohorts of students more likely to experience such difficulties (Smyth et al., 2004). Factors relating to such variance will be discussed in the proceeding section.

It is important to highlight that the transition can also present opportunities for learners, having positive impacts on wellbeing and resilience (Jindal-Snape et al., 2019), as well as providing them with a solid footing in areas of achievement, behaviour and belonging (Rice et al., 2015). Further, from a learner's viewpoint, they themselves generally feel positive about the transition, attributing a high degree of importance to the move to post-primary school (Howard & Johnson, 2004). Many view the move as a "key rite of passage", with accompanying expectations of independence and of being treated as young adults (Pratt & George, 2005).

Personal Factors

Literature has identified a collage of factors which can have influence over a student's transition from primary to post-primary. Research from many countries have brought together findings which highlight the opportunities and challenges faced by students during the transition process. While many such factors relate to the school environment, this section will focus on those that are personal to the students themselves, examining how they relate to mathematical learning at this time.

Gender

Gender differences across the transition can be seen frequently in the literature. It has been shown that male students tend to settle into post-primary school more quickly, with female students experiencing more difficulties over the transition period (e.g. Smyth, 2017; Benner & Graham, 2009). With female students, on average, experiencing puberty earlier than their male counterparts, Martel (2013) highlights that this can make them more vulnerable to negative emotional outcomes in early adolescence, often resulting from social and physical comparisons with peers. Increased instances of loneliness and anxiety have also been recorded more commonly amongst female students (Benner & Graham, 2009). Symonds and Galton (2014) surmise that consequences of this phenomenon may explain the lower levels of self-esteem female students possess across the transition. The same study also shows that male students possess higher levels of disengagement from school and learning, as they seek to establish themselves in new peer groups by actively pushing against learning.

Specific to mathematics, significant gender differences are evidenced in terms of achievement and across a range of affective elements. In achievement terms, Ryan (2018) notes a significant gender disparity amongst students in first year of post-primary school, with male students outperforming girls. Further, it should be noted that where achievement levels decline across the transition, this occurs at a more rapid pace for female students (Benner & Graham, 2009). Meanwhile, Irish results from Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) shows that in fourth class, girls were more likely to hold positive attitudes towards learning mathematics (Perkins, Clerkin, & Chubb, 2020). Comparing these results to students in second year of post-primary, a gap appeared according to gender, in which boys were substantially more likely to display positive attitudes than girls. While this

trend is also reflected in data from other test countries, significantly, Irish results displayed a more severe decline in the attitudinal values for girls than the TIMSS average. A similar gender flip can be seen in relation to student engagement towards mathematics, with boys holding higher levels of engagement than girls in second year (Perkins et al., 2020). Interestingly, girls have been shown to hold higher levels of engagement towards non-mathematics specific areas in post-primary school, such as valuing learning, participation in extracurricular activities, school identification and compliance (Wang & Eccles, 2012). Finally, in relation to self-efficacy, data from a recent Irish study indicates that at the end of their first year in post-primary school, female students have noticeably lower levels of self-efficacy towards mathematics than their male counterparts (Ryan, 2018). Such a trend is also seen for students' self-concept, with a decline across the transition more prominent amongst female students (Smyth, 2017) and may indeed relate to the drop in self-esteem as noted previously.

Special Educational Needs

Students with SEN are more susceptible to negative outcomes across the transition process (White, 2020; Smyth, 2016). In the Irish context, a relevant comparative study in this area gathered data from two cohorts of students, one in sixth class and the other in first year (Foley, Foley & Curtin, 2016). Findings reveal that students with SEN face more obstacles than their peers during the transition process. Issues include taking longer to adjust to a new setting, establishing friendships, experiencing increased anxiety and being more vulnerable to bullying. Research also indicates concerns held by students with SEN and their parents regarding mathematical learning at this time (Barnes-Holmes et al., 2013). Specifically, within this study, it was found that students found academic subjects particularly difficult following the transition to post-primary, with mathematics cited more commonly than other subject areas. Further, parents of students with SEN expressed concerns about their children falling behind academically as they move to post-primary school and the level of communication with the post-primary school at the early stages of the transition process.

Adolescence

The transition from primary to post-primary occurs for the majority of students during the early stages of adolescence and is a time of personal change for students. This stage of life brings with it a raft of mental, physical and emotional changes, to which students must adapt. Adolescence can result in changes in relationships students hold. Bishop (2012) claims that for adolescents, social interactions are a critical aspect of identity formation within the area of mathematics. Symonds and Galton (2014) also highlight such influences on identity formation, with friendships and the role students play in friendship groups of relevance. Additionally, Browne (2012) warns that adolescents, in particular, can place higher priority on social relationships with their peers than on achieving high scores, reinforcing the view that one's mathematical identity can be indeed influenced by others, or at least concealed to a certain extent so as to undermine their achievements. All this is happening at a critical time in

which students are negotiating new understandings about what it means to be a mathematical learner.

While peer relations hold particular significance at this time, changes can also be witnessed in terms of the relationships between students and their parents. Smyth (2017) found the level of closeness between children and their parents declined across a four-year period, as children went from nine to thirteen years old, coinciding with their move to post-primary school. The author points out that the improved levels of autonomy in this instance may help students as they adapt to life in post-primary school, and that signs of reduced parental involvement on items like homework can reflect good levels of academic and organisational preparedness on the student's behalf.

Final Remarks

The review of the literature around the transition from primary to post-primary reveals an intricate web of social, emotional, personal, curricular and pedagogical issues, spanning a two-year time frame. This paper provides an insight into some of the personal characteristics at play that can influence students' experience of the transition and their mathematical learning at this time. It is important to note that a band of other factors relevant to this category also exist, including student age, primary school attended, the socio-economic background of family, dispositions held by the students as well as their prior achievement, all of which can play significant roles at this time. The many factors at play can make the transition a very different experience for different students, with some encountering more obstacles than others, which can be seen to influence their experience with mathematics. In this light, a single one-size-fits-all approach or support for the transition would appear difficult to conceive and even unreasonable to expect, with the needs of individual students requiring specific consideration in any such developments.

References

- Barnes-Holmes, Y., Scanlon, G., Desmond, D., Shevlin, M., & Vahey, N. (2013). A Study of Transition from Primary to Post-Primary School for Pupils with SEN: *NCSE Research Report No. 12*. Trim: NCSE.
- Benner, A. D., & Graham, S. (2009). The transition to high school as a developmental process among multi-ethnic urban youth. *Child Development*, 80, 356–376.
- Bishop, J. P. (2012). “She’s always been the smart one. I’ve always been the dumb one”: Identities in the mathematics classroom. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 43(1), 34-74.
- Browne, J. R., II (2012). *Walking the equity talk: A guide for culturally courageous leadership in school communities*. California: Corwin Press.
- Foley, T., Foley, S., & Curtin, A. (2016). Primary to Post-Primary Transition for Students with Special Educational Needs from an Irish Context. *International Journal of Special Education*, 31(2), 1-27.

- Hargreaves, A., Earl, L., & Ryan, J. (1996). *Schooling for change: Reinventing education for early adolescents*. London: The Falmer Press.
- Howard, S., & Johnson, B. (2004). Transition from primary to secondary school: Possibilities and paradoxes. Paper presented at *AARE International Education Research Conference*, Melbourne.
- Jindal-Snape, D., Cantali, D., MacGillivray, S., & Hannah, E. (2019). Primary-secondary transitions: A systematic literature review. *Social Research Series*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.
- Martel, M. (2013). Sexual selection and sex differences in the prevalence of childhood externalizing and adolescent internalizing disorders. *Psychological Bulletin*, April 19.
- Perkins, R., Clerkin, A., & Chubb, E. (2020). *Students' perspectives on learning mathematics and science: Results from TIMSS 2015 in Ireland*. Dublin: Educational Research Centre.
- Pratt, S., & George, R. (2005) Transferring friendships: Girls' and boys' friendships in the transition from primary to secondary school. *Children & Society*, 19(1): 16–26.
- Rice, F., Frederickson, N., Shelton, K. H., McManus, I. C., Riglin, L., & Ng-Knight, T. (2015). *Identifying factors that predict successful and difficult transitions to secondary school*. London: The Nuffield Foundation.
- Ryan, V. (2018). *Making the transition: A student's mathematical journey from primary to post-primary school in Ireland*. Doctoral dissertation. University of Limerick. Retrieved from https://ulir.ul.ie/bitstream/handle/10344/7060/Ryan_2018_Making.pdf?sequence=6
- Smyth, E. (2016). Social Relationships and the Transition to Secondary Education. *The Economic and Social Review*, 47(4), 451–476.
- Smyth, E. (2017). *Growing up in Ireland, Report no.5: Off to a good start? Primary school experiences and the transition to second-level education*. Dublin: Stationery Office.
- Smyth, E., McCoy, S., & Darmody, M. (2004). *Moving up: The experiences of first-year students in post-primary education*. Dublin: Liffey Press.
- Symonds, J. E., & Galton, M. (2014). Moving to the next school at age 10–14 years: An international review of psychological development at school transition. *Review of Education*, 2(1), 1-27.
- Tilleczek, K. (2007). Fresh starts/false starts: a review of literature on the transition from elementary to secondary school. Paper presented at the *Ontario Education Research Symposium*, Toronto: Ontario Ministry of Education.
- Wang, M. T., & Eccles, J. S. (2012). Social support matters: Longitudinal effects of social support on three dimensions of school engagement from middle to high school. *Child Development*, 83, 877–895.

- Waters, S., Lester, L., Wenden, E., & Cross, D. (2012). A theoretical grounded exploration of the social and emotional outcomes of transition to secondary school. *Australian Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 22(2), 190–205.
- West, P., Sweeting, H., & Young, R. (2010). Transition matters: Pupils' experiences of the primary– secondary school transition in the West of Scotland and consequences for well-being and attainment. *Research Papers in Education*, 25(1), 21–50.
- White, J. (2020). *Supporting children's mental health and wellbeing at transition from primary to secondary school: Evidence review*. Edinburgh: NHS Health Scotland.